

PROPERTIES OF ACTIVATED SUGAR CHARCOAL COATED WITH VARIOUS ORGANIC SUB- STANCES. PART II. ADSORPTION OF ACIDS.

BY HARENDRA KUMAR ACHARYA.

In a previous paper (Acharya, *J Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 723) a method has been described of depositing acidic and alkaline coats on the surface of activated sugar charcoal. The relation between such coats and the adsorption of acids has been investigated in the present paper.

It appears that centres with basic or acidic properties should adsorb respectively acids or bases. The adsorption of benzoic acid by activated sugar charcoal, was chosen as an index to changes in the acid adsorbing properties. It appears that a distinction should be made between a direct adsorption of acids or bases by carbon atoms on the surface, and an indirect or secondary adsorption through the already adsorbed basic or acidic molecules or groups respectively which are present on the surface.

In discussing the results obtained in this paper it is necessary to obtain some estimate of the specific surface (*i. e.*, area of surface per gram) of the charcoal. The estimates of different authors vary widely from 0.9 to 1000 sq. metres (Lamb, Wilson and Chaney, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1919, 11, 420; Williams, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1919, A96, 287; Lowry and Hulett, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 1393; Ruff, Ebert and Luft, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1928, 170, 49; Marshall and Bramston-Cook, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 2019). The specific surface is generally calculated from the adsorption isotherms of suitable substances. The value thus obtained depends, however, on the choice of the adsorbates. Thus Paneth and Radu (*Ber.*, 1924, 57B, 1221) found that areas per g. of a sample of charcoal range from 46.2—268 sq. metres for different adsorbates. The estimations of Lowry (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, 34, 63), according to which the surface of 23 samples of charcoal ranged from 0.9—32.2 sq. metres, will be used for the discussion of the results given in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The sugar charcoal used in the following experiments was obtained by activating pure sugar charcoal at 800° for six hours in air at a pressure of

1 mm. The resulting charcoal had a small negative charge in contact with water. The coatings were produced as follows:

5 G. of the charcoal were kept for 24 hours in contact with 10 c.c. of an alcoholic solution containing a definite amount of the organic substance. The alcohol was next evaporated and the charcoal dried in a silica crucible on a water-bath.

For the adsorption experiments, 50 c. c. of the acid solution and 0.5 g. of the charcoal were used in each case. After 24 hours the supernatant liquids were separated by a powerful centrifuge and titrated against standard solutions of baryta using phenolphthalein as the indicator.

TABLE I.

Adsorption of benzoic acid.

Amount of the substance per g. of charcoal.	Concentration of the acid		Amount adsorbed (m. equiv. per g. of charcoal).
	Initial.	End.	
Original activated charcoal. (cf. curve 1)	0.02 N	0.01476 N	0.524
	0.0125	0.00745	0.505
	0.01	0.00520	0.480
	0.0075	0.00315	0.435
	0.005	0.00137	0.363
0.01 G. of <i>α</i> -naphthylamine (cf. curve 2)	0.02	0.00761	1.239
	0.0125	0.00394	0.856
	0.01	0.00275	0.725
	0.0075	0.00154	0.596
	0.005	0.00068	0.432
0.01 G. of diphenylamine (cf. curve 3)	0.02	0.00845	1.355
	0.0125	0.00474	0.776
	0.01	0.00347	0.653
	0.0075	0.00221	0.529
	0.005	0.00110	0.390

Amount of the substance per g. of charcoal.	Concentration of the acid		Amount absorbed (m. equiv. per g. of charcoal).
	Initial.	End.	
0.01 G. of lauric acid (cf. curve 4)	0.02	0.01530	0.470
	0.0125	0.00855	0.395
	0.01	0.00630	0.370
	0.0075	0.00402	0.348
	0.005	0.00179	0.321
0.01 G. of myristic acid (cf. curve 5)	0.02	0.01568	0.432
	0.0125	0.00870	0.380
	0.01	0.00640	0.360
	0.0075	0.00408	0.342
	0.005	0.00185	0.315
0.01 G. of palmitic acid (cf. curve 6)	0.02	0.01921	0.579
	0.0125	0.01188	0.562
	0.01	0.00947	0.553
	0.0075	0.00702	0.548
	0.005	0.00465	0.535
0.01 G. of stearic acid (cf. curve 7)	0.02	0.01890	0.510
	0.0125	0.01168	0.582
	0.01	0.00932	0.568
	0.0075	0.00694	0.556
	0.005	0.00456	0.544

Table I shows that the amine coats increase the adsorption of benzoic acid by more than 100%, *o*-naphthylamine coat being more effective than that of diphenylamine. (Fig. 1, curves 1, 2 and 3). On the other hand coats with different acids diminish the adsorption of the same to different extents, the order being palmitic acid > stearic acid > myristic acid > lauric acid. (Fig. 1, curves 4, 5, 6 and 7).

Curves 1—7 refer respectively to original charcoal, and charcoal coated with α -naphthylamine, diphenylamine, lauric, myristic, palmitic and stearic acids.

The following results show that the interaction between the pure amine and benzoic acid cannot account for the increase in adsorption of benzoic acid. The charcoal surface thus plays a definite rôle in this respect. 0.005 G. of α -naphthylamine was shaken with 50 c. c. of the benzoic acid solution of different concentrations.

TABLE II.

Concentration of the acid Initial.	End.	Amount adsorbed (m. equiv. per g. of charcoal).
0.02N	0.02N	Nil
0.0125	0.0125	"
0.01	0.01	"
0.0075	0.0075	"
0.005	0.005	"

The spreading of the amine molecules on the charcoal surface would expose them to possible interactions, and the amine molecules are probably linked to the surface atoms by chemical valences, and orientation perhaps intensify their capacity to react with acid molecules. In the latter case, we should expect a maximum adsorption of benzoic acid when the whole charcoal surface is covered with a monomolecular layer of the amine. The adsorption of benzoic acid thus passes through a peak value as shown in Table III.

TABLE III.

Amount of the substance per g. of charcoal.	Concentration of the acid Initial.	End.	Amount adsorbed (m. equiv. per g. of charcoal).
0.005 G. of <i>a</i> -naphthylamine (<i>cf.</i> curve 8)	0.02N	0.01340N	0.660
	0.0125	0.00640	0.610
	0.01	0.00450	0.550
	0.0075	0.00246	0.504
	0.005	0.00074	0.426
0.01 G. of <i>a</i> -naphthylamine (<i>cf.</i> curve 2)	0.02	0.00761	1.239
	0.0125	0.00394	0.856
	0.01	0.00275	0.725
	0.0075	0.00154	0.596
	0.005	0.00068	0.432
0.05 G. of <i>a</i> -naphthylamine (curve 9)	0.02	0.01950	0.050
	0.0125	0.01210	0.040
	0.01	0.00968	0.032
	0.0075	0.00729	0.021
	0.005	0.00483	0.017

With 0.05 g. of the amine per g. of charcoal, the adsorptive capacity of the charcoal is almost negligible, while with 0.005 g. of the same an isotherm curve with greater adsorption than the original charcoal is obtained. The maximum adsorption of the acid (0.02N) occurs with 0.01 g. of the amine per g. of charcoal, being above 135% greater than that on the original (uncoated) charcoal (Fig. 2, curves 2, 8 and 9).

FIG. 2.

Curves 2, 8 and 9 refer respectively to 0.01g., 0.005 g. and 0.05 g. of α -naphthylamine.

The maximum adsorption of benzoic acid by 'coated' charcoal is 1.239 m. equiv. Schroder (*Ber.*, 1879, 12, 562) finds the density of benzoic acid to be 1.292. Assuming the molecules to be cubes and to be spread as a continuous unimolecular layer, the above value of the maximum adsorption gives the specific area of the covered surface to be 288 sq. meters. The same method of calculation gives 101 sq. metres as the specific surface of the charcoal before the coating was applied. This value corresponds to the maximum adsorption 0.524 m. equiv. (*cf.* Fig. 1, curve 1).

Approximate values of the areas, which can be covered by a unimolecular film of the substances forming the coats, are given in Table IV. The cross section of the molecules, calculated by Adam (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1922, A101, 452) from surface pressure measurements and the density data of the amines (Dunstan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 668), have been used for this purpose.

TABLE IV.

Substance.	Amount per g. of charcoal.	Cross-section in Sq. Å.	Density.	Approximate area in sq. metres.
Lauric acid	0.01	20.5	—	6.21
Myristic acid	"	"	—	5.55
Palmitic acid	"	"	—	4.96
Stearic acid	"	"	—	4.35
Diphenylamine	"	—	1.162 ^g	16.71
α -Naphthylamine	0.001	—	1.171 ^g	1.77
	0.005	—	"	8.83
	0.01	—	"	17.66
	0.05	—	"	88.30

If we consider Lowry's (*loc. cit.*) limiting value (32.2 sq. meters) as the area for the present sample of charcoal, the different amounts of the coating substances, if spread unimolecularly, appear to be insufficient to cover the whole surface, while the maximum quantity of α -naphthylamine used for the coat (0.05 g.) may cover the total charcoal surface and form more than two layers. But the surface as calculated from the adsorption isotherm of benzoic acid on the original charcoal is 101 sq. metres. If this latter value is taken to be more reliable then it is necessary to conclude that the surface is not fully coated when the adsorption is totally stopped. It is necessary to point out that the method of producing the coat entails the possibility that the coating substances cover the exterior surface of the granules and prevent an ingress of the adsorbate to the internal surfaces.

It is, however, difficult to explain the larger adsorption of benzoic acid. 0.01 G. of amine would contain 4.24×10^{19} molecules, whereas one g. of the charcoal, coated with this amount of the amine, shows an increase in adsorption of 4.33×10^{20} molecules of benzoic acid. It is evident that the amine groups on the surface are not the only places where single molecules of benzoic acid are adsorbed. One has to assume that either each amine group on the surface adsorbs more than one molecule of benzoic acid or the coating material increases the active surface where benzoic acid is adsorbed.

With a view to confirm the above results with benzoic acid, the adsorption of salicylic, succinic and oxalic acids was also carried out at one concentration, *viz.*, 0.01N. The results are given in Tables V, VI and VII.

TABLE V.
Adsorption of salicylic acid.

Amount of the substance per g. of charcoal	Und. conc. of the acid.	Amount adsorbed (m. equiv. per g. of charcoal).
Original charcoal	0.00636N	0.364
0.01 G. of lauric acid	0.00766	0.234
.. myristic acid	0.00782	0.218
.. palmitic acid	0.01	Nil
.. stearic acid	0.00979	0.021
.. diphenylamine	0.00613	0.387
0.001 α -naphthylamine	0.00648	0.392
0.005 ..	0.00536	0.464
0.01 ..	0.00593	0.407
0.05 ..	0.01	Nil

TABLE VI.
Adsorption of succinic acid.

Amount of the substance per g. of charcoal.	End. conc. of the acid.	Amount absorbed (m. equiv. per g. of charcoal).
Original charcoal	0.0068 N	0.340
0.01 G. of lauric acid	0.00774	0.226
„ myristic acid	0.00782	0.218
„ palmitic acid	0.00971	0.029
„ stearic acid	0.00966	0.034
„ diphenylamine	0.00638	0.632
0.001 α -naphthylamine	0.00649	0.351
0.005 „	0.00570	0.430
0.01 „	0.00585	0.415
0.05 „	0.00997	Nil

TABLE VII.
Adsorption of oxalic acid.

Amount of the substance per g. of charcoal.	End conc. of the acid.	Amount adsorbed (m. equiv. per g. of charcoal).
Original charcoal	0.00836N	0.164
0.01 G. of lauric acid	0.00859	0.141
„ myristic acid	0.00882	0.118
„ palmitic acid	0.00996	Nil
„ stearic acid	0.00971	0.029
„ diphenylamine	0.00802	0.198
0.001 α -naphthylamine	0.00809	0.191
0.005 „	0.00764	0.236
0.01 „	0.00787	0.213
0.05 „	0.00989	Nil

The results in Tables V, VI and VII are quite in agreement with those obtained with benzoic acid. The different acid coats, perhaps act as a poison towards the adsorption of the acids to different extents. The adsorption of the acids on the other hand is increased with increasing amount of the amine coat and appears to pass through a maximum; further when the amount of the coat is sufficiently increased, the adsorption is totally stopped. The maximum increase in adsorption with the amine coat, which occurs when 0.005 g. of α -naphthylamine is spread per g. of charcoal, is about 25% with salicylic acid, 25% with succinic acid and 40% with oxalic acid.

The decrease in the adsorption of the acids in contact with the charcoal, coated with different acids, may be expected to be the result of some of the acid coat coming out into the solution and increasing the titratable acid. But it has been shown in Part I of this series (*loc. cit.*) that the p_H values of conductivity water, kept in contact for 24 hours with the above coats, are never less than 5. The solubility of the coats has thus little to do with the decrease in adsorption.

S U M M A R Y.

1. Coats of various organic substances, such as lauric, myristic, palmitic and stearic acids and α -naphthyl and diphenylamines have been produced on activated sugar charcoal and the influence of such coats on the adsorption of benzoic, salicylic, succinic and oxalic acids by charcoal has been studied.

2. The amine coats greatly increase the adsorption of the acids, an α -naphthylamine coat being more effective than that of diphenylamine. This increase reaches a maximum as the amount of the amine used for coating the charcoal is increased, but with further increase, the adsorption decreases to zero. The maximum increment in the adsorption of benzoic acid (0.02N) which has been observed is more than 135%, and occurs with 0.01 g. of α -naphthylamine per g. of charcoal. The maximum adsorption of salicylic, succinic and oxalic acids (0.01N) occurs with 0.005 g. of the amine and is of the order of 25% to 45%. The maximum adsorption of benzoic acid, assuming that the adsorbed molecules are spread unimolecularly on the surface, gives a value of 288 sq. meters for the specific surface.

3. The different acid coats, on the other hand, decrease the adsorption of the acids to different extents. The capacity of the coats to diminish the adsorption of the acids is of the order: palmitic acid > stearic acid > myristic acid > lauric acid.

My best thanks are due to Prof. J. N. Mukherjee for his advice and facilities for this work.